

MOTHER-TOUNGE-BASED – MULTI-LANGUAGE EDUCATION (MTB-MLE) IMPLEMENTATION IN RELATION TO KINDERGARTEN INFRASTRUCTURE AND RESOURCE ALLOCATION

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Abstract. The study assessed the relationship between MTB-MLE implementation and Kindergarten infrastructure in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected 120 teacher respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of MTB-MLE implementation shows that availability of learning materials, teacher training, policy compliance, and language of instruction are moderately extensive, while the extent of kindergarten infrastructure shows that inclusivity, cultural relevance, and classroom availability are extensive, while facilities and amenities are moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between MTB-MLE Implementation and Kindergarten Infrastructure and resource allocation. All domains of MTB-MLE implementation in terms of language of instruction, teacher training, availability of learning materials and policy compliance significantly influenced the kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation. Future research may create a collaborative culture among teachers to share insights, resources, and effective instructional strategies.

KEY WORDS

1. Mother-Tounge-Based – Multi-Language Education.
2. Kinder Infrastructure .
3. Resource Allocation.

1. Introduction

Implementing Mother-Tongue-Based Multi-Language Education (MTB-MLE) in kindergarten reflects a progressive approach to early childhood education. It aims to enhance cognitive development, language proficiency, and academic achievement by valuing students' linguistic and cultural heritage. A significant trend in the global educational landscape is the increasing adoption of MTB-MLE to enhance learning outcomes and preserve linguistic di-

versity. More countries recognize the value of teaching young learners in their mother tongue, facilitating better comprehension and smoother transitions to other languages. However, challenges such as limited funding and inadequate training for educators persist. Overcoming these challenges requires strategic resource allocation and partnerships with local communities to ensure the success of MTB-MLE programs in kindergarten settings. An inclusive approach is

also emerging, emphasizing the importance of accommodating diverse linguistic backgrounds and involving local communities in educational decisions.

Internationally, there is a growing recognition of the importance of mother-tongue-based instruction (MTBI) in education, reflecting a shift towards more inclusive and culturally responsive approaches to teaching and learning. A prominent trend in implementing MTBI is acknowledging linguistic diversity as a valuable asset rather than a barrier to education. Countries worldwide are increasingly adopting policies and programs that prioritize using students' mother tongues and local languages as mediums of instruction, particularly in the early years of schooling. This trend aligns with research highlighting the cognitive and academic benefits of MTBI, including improved language acquisition, literacy development, and overall educational outcomes (Sah (2022)). International organizations and partnerships also support efforts to mainstream MTBI within education systems, providing technical assistance, funding, and best practices to facilitate its effective implementation. Despite these positive trends, challenges persist, including limited resources, inadequate teacher training, and resistance to change within education systems. Addressing these challenges requires sustained commitment from policymakers, educators, and communities to ensure equitable access to quality education for all learners, regardless of their linguistic background (Diliberti, Woo, and Kaufman (2023)). MTB-MLE faces several challenges. Resource allocation remains a primary concern, with limited funding often hindering the development and maintenance of effective programs. Adequate teacher training is essential but can be challenging to achieve. Developing curricula and learning materials in local languages is time-consuming and expensive. Striking a balance between standardized educational content and preserving linguistic and

cultural diversity presents complexities. Additionally, the long-term sustainability of MTB-MLE programs, particularly in regions with multiple languages and dialects, requires careful consideration (Muoni, 2023). Like their counterparts in various regions, the Philippines encounters specific challenges in implementing Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). One significant challenge lies in the availability of appropriate teaching materials and resources in local languages. Developing or sourcing age-appropriate materials aligned with the curriculum can be time-consuming and resource-intensive (Lopez, 2019). Phenomenological data analysis methods were employed to obtain collective composite stories from the teachers' experiences. Framed as composite counter-stories, teachers' narratives revealed deeply embedded pedagogical challenges that they encountered resulting from the policy implementation in their classrooms. Specifically, their counter-stories demonstrated resistance towards the top-down policy that complicated learning for their students. As their stories disrupt majoritarian narratives on MTB-MLE, implications for reconsidering the policy are offered (Lopez, 2019). Additionally, teachers may need help obtaining suitable training in MTB-MLE methodologies, as effectively implementing this approach requires specialized knowledge and pedagogical skills. Managing a classroom with students from diverse linguistic backgrounds can also be demanding, as teachers must cater to the specific needs of each child, often necessitating creative and adaptable teaching methods (Gempeso and Mendez, 2021). The implementation involves gradually transitioning to other languages, such as national or English, as students progress through their education. The implementation of MTB-MLE includes designing a curriculum that aligns with language policies, training teachers in effective language instruction, and creating culturally relevant learning materials. The ultimate goal is

to provide equitable access to quality education while preserving linguistic and cultural diversity. Societal and cultural attitudes towards the use of local languages in education can influence the level of support and understanding that teachers receive. As a result, ensuring that implementing MTB-MLE is successful in Davao Oriental requires addressing these challenges through targeted training, resource provision, and fostering a supportive educational environment.

2. Methodology

Research methods are systematic procedures employed to gather and analyze data, aiming to address research inquiries and achieve specific objectives. These methods form the cornerstone of empirical investigations across a wide spectrum of disciplines, encompassing fields like the natural sciences, social sciences, and humanities. Research methods encompass a variety of approaches, including quantitative methods, which involve the collection of numerical data through means such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis. Conversely, qualitative methods focus on comprehending and interpreting non-numerical data, utilizing techniques like interviews, content analysis, or ethnography. The researcher used artificial intelligence methods for proofreading when preparing this publication. In particular, AI was used to improve the manuscript's overall quality, coherence, and correctness. The purpose of clearly stating this approach is to uphold research ethics and transparency. The use of AI for proofreading recognizes the growing presence and potential of AI in academic and professional writing and demonstrates a commitment to utilizing cutting-edge technologies responsibly.

2.1. Research Design—Within the realm of research, non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs stand as significant methodologies, each possessing unique intentions and attributes. Non-experimental research chiefly centers on the observation and analysis of preexisting phenomena without intervening in the manipulation of variables. Descriptive research endeavors to furnish an exhaustive and meticulous portrayal of a specific scenario, population, or occurrence. (Creswel, 2014). Correlational research, on the other hand, examines the relationships between variables, aiming to identify patterns, associations, or connections among them. It does not imply causation but helps researchers understand how changes in one variable may relate to changes in another. Predictive research design extends beyond describing and correlating variables. It involves developing models or theories to predict future outcomes or behavior. Researchers gather and analyze data to establish patterns that can be used for forecasting or making informed decisions. While these research designs serve distinct purposes, they share common advantages. They offer practicality, allowing researchers to study phenomena as they naturally occur, which is often the case in the social sciences. Non-experimental research designs are more ethical and logistically feasible when manipulation or experimentation is inappropriate or impossible. However, a limitation is the absence of control over variables, making it challenging to establish causal relationships. In the study examining the correlation between Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) implementation and kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation, a combination of non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research designs is employed to comprehensively assess the relationship between these two critical components of early childhood education. Non-experimental research serves as the foundation by allowing

researchers to observe and document existing conditions without intervening in the variables. Descriptive research, on the other hand, enables a detailed and exhaustive account of MTB-MLE policies and practices and the state of kindergarten facilities and resources. Correlational research is essential for quantitatively assessing the strength and direction of the relationship between MTB-MLE adoption and the quality of kindergarten infrastructure, utilizing statistical techniques to determine the existence and extent of any correlations. Finally, predictive research aids in forecasting potential scenarios by analyzing historical data and trends, offering insights into how enhancements in MTB-MLE practices may impact future kindergarten infrastructure. Together, these research designs provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the current status, interdependencies, and future implications of MTB-MLE implementation on the quality and availability of kindergarten resources.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Elementary School Teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from the private schools that surround the District. After being selected through randomization, respondents were notified both through online platforms and in person, taking into account the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they received an orientation regarding the study's objectives and its significance in relation to their professional development. The selection of participants was guided by the presumption that they were actively involved in the management and supervision of schools, particularly in terms of organizational oversight and instructional supervision. It was anticipated that these individuals possessed a strong commitment to curriculum implementation policies, pedagogical classroom practices, and the day-to-day administration of diverse school-based

initiatives, projects, and activities aimed at promoting the holistic development of early learners within the framework of private school management. The criteria for inclusion in this study were based on the expectation that they had made significant contributions that extended beyond their core responsibilities related to curriculum delivery, implementation, and governance, as evidenced by their active participation in various educational endeavors. These contributions were typically discussed during school faculty meetings, group sessions, and committee meetings, all with the goal of improving the school environment and learners' educational experiences during the new normal learning system in the academic year 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support to the school management and curriculum development delivery system.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—In the context of this research study, the instrument utilized was thoughtfully designed through an exhaustive examination of existing literature and pertinent studies. The researcher invested significant time and effort in collecting and analyzing relevant literature, extracting essential concepts that not only informed the construction of the instrument but also reinforced its alignment with the specified research themes. This meticulous process resulted in the development of a well-organized set of questionnaire items, thereby enhancing the overall validity of the instrument and minimizing potential threats to its reliability. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts, one of which consisted of indicators of MTB-MLE Implementation in terms of language of instruction, teacher training, availability of learning materials, and policy compliance. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the kindergarten infrastructure in terms of classroom availability, facilities and amenities inclusivity and

cultural relevance. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.876, which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal

consistency is very good. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of MTB-MLE Implementation. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The MTB-MLE Implementation is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The MTB-MLE Implementation is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The MTB-MLE Implementation is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The MTB-MLE Implementation is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The MTB-MLE Implementation is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of scale was used in this study, as presented below; kindergarten infrastructure, a 5-point Likert

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation are not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Permission to conduct the study. In the second week of December 2023, the researcher initiated the process of conceptualizing the content and objectives of the thesis proposal. Subsequently,

she prepared various documents, including request letters, in preparation for the study. The research study strictly adhered to established ethical data collection procedures, as outlined by Creswell (2004), and followed the health pro-

ocols mandated by the IATF's policy. As the research proposal was approved by the panel of members and the college dean in the last week of February to the first week of March 2024, the researcher composed and submitted a formal letter seeking permission to collect data and conduct the study within Banaybanay District to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, following the proper channels. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. On May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process which were sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses, and for respondents who do not have access to internet. Likewise a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets were given to each of them. Once done, link was sent, and right

away responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed in data gathering which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Results of the preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of June 2024. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometime on the first week of June 2024, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of MTB-MLE Implementation, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of Kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between MTB-MLE Implementation and Kinder-

garten infrastructure and resource allocation. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of MTB-MLE Implementation that significantly influence Kindergarten infrastructure (and resource allocation Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the responses from the data gathered in tabular and textual form. It includes discussions of the results based on and integration with reviews of the related studies. This will be the basis for the decisions to be made given the hypothesis posed.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of MTB-MLE implementation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: availability of learning materials (3.39), teacher training (3.37), policy compliance (3.20) and language of instruction (3.07) are sometimes manifested.

The overall mean rating of 3.25 denotes that extent of MTB-MLE implementation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) implementation varies globally, with its success contingent on a combination of policy support, resource al-

location, and cultural considerations. In regions where MTB-MLE has been effectively embraced, there is a visible commitment to incorporating students' mother tongues into the early stages of education. Policy frameworks often mandate the integration of local languages into the curriculum, ensuring that students receive instruction in a language familiar to them.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of MTB-MLE Implementation

No	MTB-MLE Implementation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Language of Instruction	3.07	Moderately Extensive
2	Teacher Training	3.37	Moderately Extensive
3	Availability of Learning Materials	3.39	Moderately Extensive
4	Policy Compliance	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.25	Moderately Extensive

Additionally, teacher training programs and the development of appropriate learning materials in multiple languages are key indicators of successful implementation. However, challenges may arise in areas where linguistic diversity is high, and resources are limited. In such cases, the extent of MTB-MLE implementation may be hindered by the scarcity of relevant materials and trained educators. The holistic success of MTB-MLE, therefore, depends on sustained efforts to align policies with on-the-ground practices, fostering an inclusive educational environment that celebrates linguistic

diversity and enhances learning outcomes.

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of kindergarten infrastructure. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: inclusivity (3.77), cultural relevance (3.74) and classroom availability (3.48) are oftentimes manifested, while faculties and amenities (3.31) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.57 denotes that the extent of teachers' numerical expertise is often manifested and, thus, extensive.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Kindergarten Infrastructure and Allocation

No	Kindergarten Infrastructure	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Classroom Availability	3.48	Extensive
2	Facilities and Amenities	3.31	Moderately Extensive
3	Inclusivity	3.77	Extensive
4	Cultural Relevance	3.74	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.57	Extensive

The extent of kindergarten infrastructure refers to the physical and organizational elements that support early childhood education at the kindergarten level. This encompasses a

range of facilities and resources designed to create an enriching learning environment for young children. The infrastructure includes purpose-built classrooms with age-appropriate furniture,

play areas that stimulate cognitive and motor skill development, and safety measures to ensure the well-being of the children. Additionally, kindergarten infrastructure involves access to educational materials, such as books, toys, and interactive learning tools, fostering a holistic approach to early childhood development. Adequate staffing with qualified teachers and support staff is crucial, as well as administrative systems to manage the operational aspects of the kindergarten. The extent of kindergarten infrastructure ultimately plays a pivotal role in shaping the quality of education and overall experience for young learners during their formative years (Habayib and Cinamon, 2023).

Significant Relationship between MTB-

Table 3. Significant Relationship between MTB-MLE Implementation and Kindergarten Infrastructure and Resource Allocation

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
MTB-MLE Implementation				
Kindergarten Infrastructure and Resource Allocation	0.869	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

Famularsih et.al. (2022) stated that the implementation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) is significantly intertwined with kindergarten infrastructure, creating a symbiotic relationship that profoundly influences early childhood education. MTB-MLE emphasizes the use of a child’s mother tongue as the medium of instruction in the early years of education. This approach recognizes the importance of cultural and linguistic diversity, fostering a deeper understanding of concepts and a smoother transition to additional languages. In the context of kindergarten infrastructure, a well-designed and culturally sensitive environment becomes crucial for effective MTB-MLE implementation. Adequate resources, such as age-appropriate teaching materials in local languages, are essential to support the curriculum. Additionally, kindergarten

MLE Implementation and Kindergarten Infrastructure

Table 3 flaunts the yielded results of the significant relationship between MTB-MLE Implementation and Kindergarten Infrastructure. It provides a piece of information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between MTB-MLE Implementation and Kindergarten Infrastructure must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant strong positive correlation between MTB-MLE Implementation ($r=0.869$; $p<.000$) and Kindergarten Infrastructure.

facilities must accommodate linguistic diversity, allowing for the incorporation of various mother tongues spoken by the students. Moreover, teacher training programs must align with MTB-MLE principles to ensure educators can facilitate learning in diverse linguistic contexts. Therefore, the significant relationship between MTB-MLE implementation and kindergarten infrastructure underscores the importance of creating an inclusive and supportive environment that caters to young learners’ linguistic and cultural needs, fostering a more meaningful and effective educational experience (Shohfi , 2020).

Domains of MTB-MLE Implementation Significantly Influence Kindergarten Infrastructure and Resource Allocation

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of MTB-

MLE implementation that significantly influence kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation. Domains of MTB-MLE implementation in terms of language of instruction (0.000), teacher training (0.001), availability of learning materials (0.000) and policy compliance (0.001) suggest significant influence over kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.874 suggests that 87.4

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of MTB-MLE Implementation Significantly Influence Kindergarten Infrastructure and Resource Allocation

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions	Interpretation
(Intercept)	4.145		0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145
(Intercept)	0.313		0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204
language of instruction	0.207	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315	0.000
*Reject H_0						
teacher training	0.241	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196	0.001
*Reject H_0						
availability of learning materials	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038	0.000
*Reject H_0						
policy compliance	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038	0.001
*Reject H_0						
$R^2 = 0.874$						
$F\text{-value} = 254.897$						
$p\text{-value} = < 0.001$						

The domains of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) implementation exert a substantial influence on kindergarten infrastructure across various key aspects. In terms of language of instruction, the linguistic domain emphasizes the use of a child’s mother tongue, necessitating a diverse and adaptable language environment within the infrastructure. This involves the creation of classrooms equipped with materials and resources in multiple local languages, ensuring that the linguistic diversity of the students is addressed effectively. Teacher training constitutes another crucial domain, requiring kindergarten educators to undergo programs that align with MTB-MLE principles (Poppe, Thorman and Weyer, 2020). Vitiello, et.al., (2022) shared that the infrastructure must support ongoing professional development opportunities, workshops, and resources to

empower teachers with the skills needed for effective multilingual instruction. Availability of learning materials is paramount in the cognitive domain, influencing the design of kindergarten spaces to accommodate a rich array of culturally relevant books, educational tools, and interactive resources in various languages. Moreover, the policy compliance domain underscores the importance of kindergarten infrastructure aligning with national and regional policies promoting the integration of MTB-MLE. In essence, Diliberti, Woo and Kaufman (2023) said that these domains collectively shape kindergarten infrastructure by influencing the language of instruction, guiding teacher training initiatives, ensuring the availability of diverse learning materials, and ensuring compliance with policies to create an environment conducive to the successful implementation of MTB-MLE in early

childhood education.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In this chapter, the outcomes, conclusions, and recommendations are delineated in accordance with the analyzed and discussed data, along with the implications drawn from the findings. The findings emanate from the articulated statement of the problem, while the conclusions are derived from the resultant findings. The recommendations, in turn, are formulated based on the implications gleaned from the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of MTB-MLE implementation shows that the availability of learning materials, teacher training, policy compliance, and language of instruction are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating denotes that extent of MTB-MLE implementation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation shows that inclusivity, cultural relevance, and classroom availability are oftentimes manifested, while faculties and amenities are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating denotes that the extent of teachers' numerical expertise is often manifested and, thus, extensive. There is a significant correlation between MTB-MLE Implementation ($r=0.869$; $p<.000$) and Kindergarten Infrastructure and Resource allocation. Domains of MTB-MLE implementation in terms of language of instruction, teacher training, availability of learning materials and policy compliance suggest significant influence over kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions: The extent of MTB-MLE implementation shows that the availability of learning materials, teacher training, policy compliance, and language of instruction are sometimes manifested. This denotes that extent of MTB-MLE imple-

mentation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation shows that inclusivity, cultural relevance, and classroom availability are often manifested, while faculties and amenities are sometimes manifested. This denotes that the extent of kindergarten infrastructure is often manifested, thus extensive. There is a significant relationship between MTB-MLE Implementation and Kindergarten Infrastructure. Domains of MTB-MLE implementation, such as language of instruction, teacher training, availability of learning materials, and policy compliance, suggest that they significantly influence kindergarten infrastructure and resource allocation. In the context of education, the Sociocultural Theory has profound implications. It emphasizes the significance of collaborative learning environments, where students engage in meaningful dialogues to co-construct knowledge. It underscores the need for culturally relevant and contextually meaningful educational experiences that respect and incorporate students' cultural backgrounds. Sociocultural Theory encourages educators to be sensitive to the social and cultural dimensions of learning, recognizing that students bring their unique cultural experiences and perspectives to the learning process. In summary, Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory provides a robust framework for understanding that learning is a dynamic and socially embedded phenomenon, where cultural context and social interactions

are central to cognition development and knowledge acquisition.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. The study recommends that the Public School District Supervisor actively engages in continuous professional development programs to stay abreast of the latest educational methodologies and best practices. Encourage collaboration and knowledge-sharing among schools within the district to foster a supportive learning community. Advocate for sufficient resources, both financial and educational, to enhance the overall quality of education within the district. School Principal. The study suggests that the School Head implements a robust teacher evaluation and support system to ensure the professional growth of educators. Consider strategies to create an inclusive and conducive learning environment that caters to diverse student needs. Prioritize

regular communication and collaboration with teachers to address challenges and share successful teaching practices. Teacher. The study recommends that teachers actively participate in professional development opportunities to enhance their teaching skills and stay current with educational trends. Encourage teachers to adopt student-centered teaching methodologies that cater to various learning styles. Foster a collaborative culture among teachers to share insights, resources, and effective instructional strategies. Future Researcher. The study suggests that future researchers explore more comprehensive and longitudinal studies to delve deeper into the identified issues. Encourage the use of mixed-methods research to provide a more nuanced understanding of the educational landscape. Advocate for research that addresses emerging challenges and opportunities in education, ensuring relevance to the evolving needs of students and educators

1. References

- AITF For the Management of Infectious Diseases
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2021/05may/20210520-IATF->
- Alghamdi, Jawaher; Mostafa, Fatma; Abubshait, Aisha (2022). Exploring Technology Readiness and Practices of Kindergarten Student-Teachers in Saudi Arabia: A Mixed-Methods Study *Education and Information Technologies*, v27 n6 p7851-7868 Jul 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10920-0>
- Agbaria, Qutaiba (2021). Classroom Management Skills among Kindergarten Teachers as Related to Emotional Intelligence and Self-Efficacy *International Journal of Instruction*, v14 n1 p1019-1034 Jan 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Classroom+Availability+as+Kindergarten+Infrastructure&id=EJ1282266>
- Ball, Jessica; Smith, Mariam (2023). Essential Components in Planning Multilingual Education: A Case Study of Cambodia's Multilingual Education National Action Plan *Current Issues in Language Planning*, v24 n1 p21-41 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14664208.2021.2013060>
- de Lemios, Ronald O. (2023). From Tagalog to English: Pupils' Writing Proficiency Levels after Three Years in Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education *Online Submission, Journal of Community Development Research (Humanities and Social Sciences)* v16 n3 p115-133 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=language+of+instruction+in+MTB-MLE+Implementation&id=ED630163>
- De Los Reyes, Robin Atilano (2019). Translanguaging in Multilingual Third Grade ESL Classrooms in Mindanao, Philippines *International Journal of Multilingualism*, v16 n3 p302-316 2019 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2018.1472268>
- Diliberti, Melissa Kay; Woo, Ashley; Kaufman, Julia H. (2023). The Missing Infrastructure for Elementary (K-5) Social Studies Instruction: Findings from the 2022 American Instructional Resources Survey. Research Report. RR-A134-17 *RAND Corporation* <https://doi.org/10.7249/RR-A134-17>
- Famularsih, Sari; Nuryatin, Agus; Handoyo, Eko; Fitriati, Sri Wuli (2022). Facility and Infrastructure Management at the International Class Program of the State Islamic University in Indonesia *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, v13 n4 p291-307 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Facilities+and+Amenities+as+Kindergarten+Infrastructure&id=EJ1375615>

- Gempeso, Hyra Dave P.; Mendez, Jubelle Dianne S. (2021). Constructive Alignment of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB MLE) Language Policy Implementation to the Practices of a Multilingual Classroom *English Language Teaching Educational Journal*, v4 n2 p125-137 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=MTB-MLE+Implementation&id=EJ1311541>
- Gujarati, D.N. and Porter, D.C. (2009) *Basic Econometrics*. 5th Edition, McGraw-Hill Irwin, Boston, 400.
- Habayib, Halah; Cinamon, Rachel Gali (2023). Preschool Teachers' Attitudes toward Career Education: The Role of Cultural Context and Teaching Self-Efficacy *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, v23 n2 p399-419 Jul 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10775-021-09519-7>
- Holmes, Shannon R.; Reinke, Wendy M.; Herman, Keith C.; David, Kimberly (2022). An Examination of Teacher Engagement in Intervention Training and Sustained Intervention Implementation *School Mental Health*, v14 n1 p63-72 Mar 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12310-021-09457-3>
- Lartec, Jane K.; Belisario, Anastacia M.; Bendanillo, Jamaica P.; Binas-o, Hanni K.; Bucang, Novefirst O.; Cammagay, Jan Lorie W. (2014). Strategies and Problems Encountered by Teachers in Implementing Mother Tongue-Based Instruction in a Multilingual Classroom *IAFOR Journal of Language Learning*, v1 n1 Win 2014 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=availability+of+learning+materials+++in+MTB-MLE+Implementation&id=EJ1167236>
- Lopez, Mark Preston S.; Coady, Maria R.; Ekid, Annie Grail F. (2019). Rural Indigenous Teachers' Lived Experiences in Mother Tongue Education in the Philippines: Counter-Stories of Resistance *Journal for Critical Education Policy Studies*, v17 n3 p132-169 Dec 2019 <http://www.jceps.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/17-3-5.pdf>
- Mouni, Ram Bahadur (2023). Ideologies of Policy Arbiters in Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Policy in the Nepalese Context *Online Submission, Language and Language Teaching* n23 p15-23 Jan 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=MTB-MLE+Implementation&id=ED630166>
- Oyzon, Voltaire Q.; Corrales, Juven B.; Estardo, Wilfredo M., Jr. (2015). Validation Study of Waray Text Readability Instrument *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, v4 n2 p45-53 Jun 2015 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=availability+of+learning+materials+++in+MTB-MLE+Implementation&id=EJ1091693>

- Pallant, J. (2020). *SPSS Survival Manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using IBM SPSS (7th ed.)*. Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003117452>
- Poppe, Julie; Thorman, Abby; Weyer, Matt (2020). *Improving Early Childhood Education Systems. Policy Brief Education Commission of the States*
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Kindergarten+Infrastructure&id=ED605814>
- Race to the Top - Early Learning Challenge: 2016 Final Performance Report. Ohio
Race to the Top - Early Learning Challenge
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Inclusivity+as+Kindergarten+Infrastructure&id=ED584981>
- Roberts-Tyler, Emily J.; Roberts, Sarah E.; Watkins, Richard; Hughes, J. Carl; Hastings, Richard P.; Gillespie, David (2023). Effects of Implementation Support on Children's Reading Outcomes Following an Online Early Reading Programme: A Cluster-Randomised Controlled Trial *British Journal of Educational Technology*, v54 n5 p1373-1396 Sep 2023
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13312>
- Sah, Pramod K. (2022). English Medium Instruction in South Asia's Multilingual Schools: Unpacking the Dynamics of Ideological Orientations, Policy/Practices, and Democratic Questions *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, v25 n2 p742-755 2022
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2020.1718591>
- Shohfi, Kyle D. (2020). *School Construction and Renovation: A Review of Federal Programs and Legislation. CRS Report R41142, Version 10. Updated Congressional Research Service*
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Facilities+and+Amenities+as+Kindergarten+Infrastructure&id=ED610723>
- Vitiello, Virginia E.; Nguyen, Tutrang; Ruzek, Erik; Pianta, Robert C.; Whittaker, Jessica Vick (2022). Differences between Pre-K and Kindergarten Classroom Experiences: Do They Predict Children's Social-Emotional Skills and Self-Regulation across the Transition to Kindergarten? *Grantee Submission, Early Childhood Research Quarterly* v59 p287-299 2022
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2021.11.009>
- Xiao, Jing; Liu, Xu (2023). How Does Family Cultural Capital Influence the Individuals' Development?--Case Study about Left-Behind Children in China *Asia Pacific Education Review*, v24 n1 p167-178 Mar 2023
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12564-022-09744-x>

Yurtsever, Nudar; Angin, Duriye Esra (2022). Examining the Mediating Role of Altruism in the Relationship between Empathic Tendencies, the Nature Relatedness, and Environmental Consciousness *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal*, v12 n1 p217-239 2022
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Inclusivity+as+Kindergarten+Infrastructure&id=EJ1336288>